

A Study on Student-Centered Educational Management

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To cite this article: Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 500 – 523. - 0099-0001-2208-03012.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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"• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

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"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

When it comes to effectively implementing a plan for training qualified managers, one of the most crucial factors that can play a role is the philosophy underlying management education. The term "critical success factors" refers to the management and organizational structures that must be set up successfully to increase the likelihood of implementation being successful. The latest wave of

technical advances has enabled changing processes to be used in an ever-increasing variety of new ways to achieve the best possible results. More consideration should be given to the idea of management education and its direct implications in conversations between businesses and educational institutions. In the field of education, management can be understood as an all-encompassing approach to the management of processes related to a wide range of social and economic sciences, as well as information resources (Lewis et al., 1995) and problem solving (conditions) for problem solving and decision making). The creation of competent managers is often the responsibility of higher education institutions. There is no doubt that one of the most effective sources of management skills in decision making is professional experience. On the other hand, teaching methods can produce scenarios, specific environments and simulated conditions that are extremely helpful tools for the development of competence and management abilities throughout postgraduate studies. In several areas linked to management education, including business partnerships, advisory services, and information and communication technology. These operational principles supply a framework for consistent decision-making and resource allocation, and boundaries for proper behavior. As a result of these factors, it should support the efforts of universities to realize their social goals and aims and will supply unity and integrity to the research and industry world. The application of these principles will result in the formation of educational institutions that focus on both students and sectors. These institutions will have a mission-oriented culture that includes the participation of management educators, students, and business managers, and they will have a better chance of being successful in realizing their vision.

Keywords: *Education, Instructor, Educational Administration, Instructor Administration, Instructional Administration*

1. Introduction

Many companies require their managers to have the skills to understand various scenarios, choose more proper solutions, and find practical solutions. It is information that meets their requirements so that they can keep their competitive level. For example, promoting a product portfolio that requires effective communication, negotiating terms of sale and creating a positive image of

responsibility and commitment are essential; therefore, an increasing number of companies are looking for strong managers. Managers also need to be effective collaborators, have strong social skills, and be able to persuade and interact with people in a variety of professional contexts according to the needs of businesses. This shows that educational institutions and the higher education they offer to the market should be brought closer. It is the responsibility of educational institutions to put this strategy into practice by engaging with the private sector in a variety of ways, such as partnerships with local companies. If this is done, future graduates will have the opportunity to gain experience from managers who have real-world ability in their industry and practical understanding of the market. These managers and executives can explain exactly what skills and knowledge new graduates need to meet the needs of various industries. Management educators can become more aligned with the materials and teaching strategies of their field by basing their decisions on the indicators and interpretations they use in their lessons. It should be noted that the education system was created not only for the benefit of students, but also to fulfill the requirements of the industry in terms of creativity and technological progress.

2. New Information and Communication Technologies in the Education Process

The importance of newly developed information and communication technologies in the context of the training process the effectiveness of management training procedures also depends on technical effort, which may include a deep technological knowledge. This is true from a strategic point of view. In this scenario, this shows that instructors should focus their attention on the following questions:

- How do students understand and use the capabilities these technologies offer?
- How can management educators be encouraged to produce higher-qualified graduates using instructional strategies based on these? What types of technologies are there?
- Is it included to generate an elevated level of knowledge to improve the quality of the options offered?

educational institutions and which should offer a competitive perspective in the market.

Learning theories can supply an explanation for the development of educational experiences for many information technology ideas. By the basic architectural principles of social cognitive learning theory, it is possible to accept that the use of e-learning technology has led to the adoption of new teaching and learning methodologies . Cognitive processes and network approaches will need to interact with each other for these paths to be followed.

To ensure the success of their programs, educational institutions should design and supply tools for continuous improvement in teaching techniques as well as continuing education for teachers. To keep their positive image and remain competitive, company executives and other personnel need to constantly renew their skills and educate themselves on emerging technology. It is highly recommended that a newcomer to the teaching profession take a shorter period of classroom instruction under the guidance of an experienced educator to buy new teaching strategies and/or improve existing teaching abilities. Additionally, educators responsible for comparable challenges can work together to find ways in which they can improve their teaching methods. Management educators and academics should direct their attention to the following factors when making judgments from various perspectives and arriving at an integrated decision:

- (1) *Use effective communication tactics with students.*
- (2) *Prove that you are knowledgeable and have a good understanding of all topics.*
- (3) *It is especially important to create and keep conducive educational environments in which students actively take part in learning social interaction, cooperative learning and self-motivation processes.*
- (4) *is essential to supply tangible evidence of effective management procedures .*
- (5) *Define and put into practice various concepts and procedures for classroom management .*
- (6) *Encourage the ability to make complex decisions in children, which means teaching them to examine a problem from various angles and then conclude that takes all these aspects into account.*
- (7) *Develop the necessary capabilities to examine various conditions as part of integrated strategic scenarios.*

- (8) *When trying to solve problems or make decisions, it is essential to have the ability to approach issues from a conceptual perspective and to use theories, models, and other forms of abstraction.*
- (9) *Developing the ability to grasp the various challenges that may be met is essential.*
- (10) *Develop your workgroups into productive task and problem-solving teams.*
- (11) *Develop the ability to come up with strategies and be involved in the procedures to put them into action .*

Collaboration between educational institutions and organizations the higher education system must set up partnerships with businesses and educational institutions to provide students with a sufficiently beneficial education both as an economic intermediary and as a service recipient. Strengthening the competitiveness of companies is always vital to foster economic growth and success. To achieve this, undergraduate programs need to be linked to the needs of the industry. Training and preparation of managers can also be improved through joint efforts between businesses and various educational institutions. It is possible to tailor programs to meet the needs of specific businesses as well as the challenges, goals and trends affecting the future of various industries. Additionally, certain collaboration programs may provide some firms with the opportunity to recruit management students on a part-time basis to collaborate with their managers. These students can use their earlier learning and further develop their abilities during this period of study. It is possible for businesses and educational institutions to work together in various programs aimed at developing professional skills and abilities, such as developing strategic business relationships among their managers. A parallel can be drawn between the link that exists between the corporate world and the higher education sector and the link that exists between companies and their respective customers.

3. People management

Typical public schools have a lower average people management score (1.92) than other school types when scores from all nationalities are added together. The difference is significant, coming in at 0.26 points and once again statistically significant, coming in at 1 percent. This conclusion is

not driven by a particular set of nations, unlike the non-human management score. The sign of the difference between the averages is the same in all eight countries, showing that regular public schools score lower on average. The difference between the averages is highest in Brazil (0.72 points), Germany (0.47 points), Sweden (0.39 points) and Italy (0.28 points) and either 5 percent or percent in each country with the exceptions. is 5.

Ordinary public schools in Brazil, Germany, Sweden and Italy have a narrower range of people management score distribution than other school types, as seen in the lower standard deviations in Table 2. This is also true in Italy. Regular public schools have a lower standard deviation in people management scores than other types of schools in the United States, Canada, India and the United Kingdom; however, the differences between regular public schools and other school types are small and do not have a statistically significant effect. Programs implemented in Brazil, Sweden, and Germany are particularly notable in that people management scores are significantly more concentrated in ordinary public schools than in other school types.

In summary, the findings of Bloom et al. show that this reexamination (of 2015 data) has two important implications. Looking at adoption trends among diverse types of schools, the first thing to do is to distinguish between management strategies that involve non-humans and management strategies that involve humans. Although the average management score in regular public schools is lower than in other schools, the average non-human management score in regular public schools is higher than in other schools in various OECD countries. This is the case in regular public schools in the United States. Management practices are not universally worse (in WMS coding) in publicly funded schools running within a public regulatory framework. This applies to regular public schools included in the WMS dataset for schools in Canada, Italy, and the United States.

Second, when looking at adoption trends among diverse types of schools, it is useful to look at differences in management practices rather than just the average, as this will throw some light on the issue. Those for both non-human and human management were lower and more tightly clustered in ordinary public schools in Brazil and Sweden compared to other types of schools. This is true for human management scores in Germany and Italy, but not for non-human management scores in both countries. The finding that schools with less operational autonomy have less

variation in management scores is, of course, clear. It also highlights how important it is to consider school management in the context of the wider education system.

4. Training Method

Bloom et al. (2015), the average score for general administration in autonomous public schools is much higher than the score in regular public schools. "What explains the usefulness of autonomous public schools?" They try to find an answer to the question. This arose as a reaction to the result described above. The positive coefficient on the autonomous public school stays stable until constraints are applied for 'principal accountability' (the extent to which the principal is accountable to institutional stakeholders such as school external boards) and 'core strategy'. In these specifications, the size of the coefficient is reduced to one-fifth of the value in the specification without extra control; this is 0.129 as opposed to 0.233. However, the coefficient is still economically and statistically significant. Another approach to thinking about the disparity in management ratings between several types of schools is to consider the issue in terms of systems.

5. System Overview?

- *Delegation. Education authorities make it clear what they want to be done, known as the goals or aims those schools and educator are usually expected to achieve.*
- *Finance. The budget for each school is decided by the relevant education authorities. It's possible that this includes things like teacher salaries and bonuses, but it's also possible that teacher salaries are decided centrally.*
- *Support. Education authorities manage developing the curriculum, as well as distributing learning materials and professional development opportunities to schools and trainers.*
- *Information. Educational authorities decide what information should be collected from schools.*

- *Motivation. Educational authorities decide what will happen to both schools and teaching staff if the findings are positive (in line with the designated delegation and based on the available information) and what will happen if they are negative. These can be seen as either good or negative, as well as internal or external (material) behavior drivers.*

The decisions made under each design aspect will have an impact on the ability of principals working in government sponsored and supervised schools to adopt management techniques that receive good grades from the WMS. If education authorities decide to keep control of teachers' salaries and distribute school resources primarily to non-human goods, principals will have little room to implement procedures that score well in 'attracting talent', one of the constituent factors. Similarly, if education officials decide not to allow performance-based rewards (bonuses and/or promotions) and sanctions (firing or reassignment/reassignment), principals will have little freedom to adopt practices that score highly on questions. This is because dismissal or reassignment will be the only options available to them. "Rewarding the top performers" and "eliminating the bad performers" are two terms often used in business. In summary, principals in ordinary public schools do not work in a vacuum; rather, they are embedded in a hierarchy of management relations within the broader public education system that is not (or is) less constrained than other systems.

If principals in regular public schools are under such structural constraints, we would expect management scores from other schools to be as low as those shown in regular public schools. Indeed, this is what we discovered in four of the eight countries that make up the WMS. It is important to keep in mind that both nonhuman and people management scores among regular public schools in Brazil and Sweden are significantly lower and significantly less dispersed compared to scores for other school groups that may be autonomous public schools. The same is true for scores on people management in Germany and Italy, though not for ratings related to other areas.

6. A Few Methods for Monitoring the Results of Students' Efforts

Some methods for monitoring student outcomes can provide school administrators and educators with useful information about their students' academic performance as well as help students become more proficient in new learning. Research in cognitive science has shown that the practice of retrieval, which involves actively seeking information from one's memory while receiving feedback on the accuracy of the information received, can improve a person's ability to remember information over a long period of time (Roediger and Butler). , 2011; see also Dunlosky et al (2013) practice testing and Ericsson et al (1993) deliberate practice for the development of expertise). Similarly, meta-analyses of treatments that aid formative assessment in grades kindergarten through twelfth have shown that these programs have a weighted average effect size of 0.20 on student achievement. Results of a recent randomized controlled trial of a formative assessment program in primary schools in Haryana, India, found that the program did not improve test scores. This has been found to be so, partly because evaluation is treated as an administrative task and partly because evaluation is seen as an administrative task (Berry et al., 2020).

In summary, there is a growing body of data suggesting that monitoring and focusing on student learning is linked to student achievement, and there is a growing body of knowledge that suggests this area of management practice presents difficult problems.

One such challenge is management. In their paper to promote WMS, Bloom and Van Reenen (2007) note that businesses may decide not to adopt certain productivity-enhancing management techniques unless the productivity benefits of adopting them outweigh the costs of implementing them. This trade-off certainly applies to the regularity and formality recommended for schools in the WMS, and the expenditure invested in the time of administrators and teachers to check school performance. According to the results of the 2018 International Teaching and Learning Survey (TALIS), nationally representative samples of secondary school teachers in 48 different countries reported that they spent an average of 8.2 percent of class time on 'general administrative tasks' such as attendance or record keeping. The survey was conducted in English.

Measurement is another hurdle. Creating correct, dependable, and properly calibrated student assessments is a process that can be resource-intensive and fraught with potential technological

challenges. On the other hand, high-quality student assessment is not only necessary for effective monitoring but also suffers when incentives built into monitoring systems do not work as intended. The quality of student assessment is discussed under the field of operations known in the WMS for schools as data-driven transitions. This means that student transitions must be "supported by formative assessment that is strongly linked to learning needs." However, the monitoring and target setting sectors are satisfied with the quality of assessment as it stands.

It is not a clever idea to ask students to find the number that corresponds to the unit position of the cube root of 531.441 in a test designed to assess their knowledge of place values. To illustrate this point with a scenario that is both frightening and factual, consider:

If we had learned the place values first, we wouldn't be experts in the much more difficult cube roots. Performance assessments that prove real-world skills, such as portfolios or graduation projects, assessed using rubrics rather than percent-correct or item-response theory scoring, have been proposed by several education professionals to replace standardized tests.

Using test results as a measure of schools or teachers' performance shows another level of validity, namely whether the measures accurately are teachers' and schools' contributions to learning, rather than reflecting elements that have no influence on them. To achieve the best possible score on the WMS's target balance metric, schools must set targets for "both absolute and value-added indicators of student outcomes" to achieve the highest possible score.

Validity is only one part of quality when it comes to assessing students; Reliability is also important. Test score data corruption when agents respond to self-serving incentives is a potential issue when using evaluation data in management processes. This has been seen in Campbell's (1979) and Goodhart's research and is a problem that can arise when using evaluation data. Reliability at the item and test design levels is also a concern. Test score manipulation ranges from focusing on children whose test scores are close to accountability thresholds (e.g., Bozer - Jennings (2005) in Texas), to inflationary tolerance in rating (e.g., Hinnerich and Vlachos (2017) in Sweden), among other methods, and directly deception (for example, Jordan) and Buckner and Hodges for Morocco (2016). Statistical analyzes of assessment data in Sweden (Diamond and

Persson , 2016), the United States (Dee et al., 2019; Jacob and Levitt , 2003) found response patterns indicating test score manipulation in southern Italy (Angrist et al., 2017), Mexico (Martinelli et al., 2018), India (Johnson and Parrado , 2020; Singh, 2020), Indonesia (Berkhout et al., 2020), and Manipulation of test scores can reveal success. This is not only because students, teachers, and administrators direct their efforts to manipulation rather than learning , but also to the fact that these individuals can make bad decisions if they treat the manipulated data as true.

As a result, high-quality student assessments must also be properly calibrated. In many low-income and middle-income countries, actual student learning falls far below the standards that many policymakers and school leaders find easy to accept. This is because of the learning crisis that exists in many countries. A recent study to evaluate the effectiveness of a computer-assisted curriculum in India found that grade 6 children assigned to the treatment group lag an average of 2.5 years in the mathematics curriculum before the study began. For example, in the Demographic and Health Surveys conducted in 51 developing countries, only half of all women aged 25-34 who finished sixth grade (but did not attend secondary school) were able to read a simple line such as "Parent". When the formal curriculum is much more advanced than the actual learning levels, prioritizing students' completion of the curriculum rather than improving their achievement causes students to fall further behind their learning aims over time.

7. People Management: Context Matters

The management of people, with the repetitive "the better the better" scale, is a subject where there is probably less agreement on the management procedures that should be included in student information systems (WMS) for schools. Due to system-level constraints, one of the factors discussed above is the possibility that principals in regular public schools may have limited discretion in adopting high-scoring practices (flexible compensation, promotion, hiring and firing). This is one of the factors discussed. If this is the case, then the discipline of people management may be more about the management of a school by the education authorities than the management of a school principal. Also, in some applications, i.e., for performance pay while rewarding great

performers, the word "more" may encourage student learning in some settings but not in others. This is because " more" can have different meanings depending on the situation.

, performance pay schemes have been proposed in two recent reviews (Glewwe and Muralidharan , 2015; Breeding et al., 2020) and a recent meta-analysis (Pham et al., 2020).

The relationship between extrinsic incentives and intrinsic drive may vary depending on circumstances, which is a potential explanation for the observed pattern of variance. According to Frey 's 1997 argument , extrinsic incentives exclude intrinsic motivation only when the perpetrator already has a high amount of intrinsic drive. The results of these experiments lend credence to this notion. Teacher performance pay schemes increased student achievement and were viewed favorably by teachers in several less well-functioning education systems (a considerable proportion of teachers did not even meet the 'basic' of coming to work and being in school). This is because these teacher performances pay schemes encourage teachers to work and attend school (Muralidharan and Sundararaman , 2011a,b), Tanzania (Mbiti et al . , 2019; Mbiti and Schipper , 2019) and Rwanda .), suggesting that extrinsic incentives can inhibit intrinsic motivation . It is also a good example that they can strengthen intrinsic motivation when it is felt that they restrict autonomy but confirm competence . This is linked to the idea that extrinsic incentives can inhibit intrinsic motivation to the extent that it is felt to constrain autonomy . The Tanzanian performance compensation scheme is another piece of evidence to support this idea. McAlpine et al. (2018), one of the reasons teachers in Tanzania have a positive impression of the program is that they view the program as a status-enhancing social endorsement, as the program includes visits from practitioners from abroad.

On the other hand, in other contexts, it was undeniably found to be 'better' when it comes to the more widespread adoption of rewarding excellence. This has been proved by three recent studies. In Uganda, a performance pay program for math teachers had no impact on school attendance, achievement or achievement in schools without math books. However, the program resulted in a slight increase in teacher participation in schools with proper books and an improvement in student performance on the test items covered in the books. Children in Pakistan had higher test scores because of the test score-based performance pay program, but this program also resulted in a

redirection of education time to evaluate preparation, which had a detrimental effect on students' socio-emotional development. And the implementation of high-stakes teacher evaluation in the states of the United States has led to an increase in the quality of new teachers (as measured by the selectivity of undergraduate institutions), but also an increased probability.

Norms can, in some cases, make it difficult to run a school. Teachers' views on who can judge their work accurately have been influenced by the social hierarchies of rank that exist, for example, in India and Indonesia. Although schools are part of the Israeli state education system, an insider study conducted by Mizel found that instructors in Bedouin schools in Israel emphasized responsibility to the tribal sheikh rather than accountability to the ministry of education (2009). Here are some examples of environments where the differences between norms and formal expectations are significant:

Sabarwal and Abu- Jawdeh (2018), more than seventy-five percent of teachers surveyed in Argentina, Senegal and Tajikistan showed that absenteeism in the classroom was acceptable before the teacher entered the classroom.

8. In-System View

The fourth issue is the need to consider the unique environment when managing people. This raises two different points. The first consideration is in terms of systems: the principal surveyed may not have the authority to make decisions about the application of high score (in WMS coding) people management techniques in certain school and national circumstances. Second, when it comes to certain practices in this area, such as the practice of rewarding high-performing teachers with performance pay, "more" may be "better" in some school and country contexts, but not in others. This is especially true for the practice of rewarding high-performing teachers with performance pay. In its current form, do the questions in the field of people management adequately address the management of school principals and is it appropriate to code the answers monotonously? Researchers may want to consider whether managing questions in the field of people management in their current form makes sense in their context. *A scale of "more is better"?*

9. Conclusion

To begin, it is vital to encourage academics and policy makers who want to compare management approaches in schools to adopt a systems view. This is a prerequisite for comparison. Second, about measuring management practices in schools, it is necessary to encourage researchers to consider how best to assess the fit between practices in the field of operations and the difficulty of measuring student learning for monitoring and goal setting purposes. This is because it is necessary to encourage researchers to consider how best to assess the fit between applications in the computing field and the challenge of measuring student learning. For the less unanimous field of people management, researchers may want to consider whether, in the context of their country, questions in the field of people management are adequately addressed by school principals and whether coding is actually appropriate. Additionally, they may want to consider whether the coding is proper. Concerns about educational institutions and business schools trying to explain and emphasize the social, political and moral aspects of management practices should be addressed by engaging more critically with the lived experience of managers through alternative pedagogical approaches and methods. Consideration of other people's needs, and perspectives is one of the hallmarks of collaboration. While not the opposite of domination, cooperation runs on an entirely different playing field. The difference between dominance and cooperation is that the latter emphasizes student and teacher working together as a team, while the former sees the teacher as the driving force in the classroom. Relationships between teachers and students are most likely to succeed when they are characterized by a balance between two competing power structures: *dominance and cooperation*. There are several different approaches that can be used to successfully generate enough teamwork. Teachers can express proper degrees of collaboration and ability by giving clear and flexible learning aims, respectively. Additionally, teachers can communicate acceptable levels of individual ability by presenting clear and flexible learning aims. A spirit of collaboration can be created by giving students the choice to define their own goals at the beginning of a lesson or by asking what they would like to learn about the topic. Take, for example, the scenario where a teacher decides to focus a teaching unit on fractions and then distributes a rubric to each student in the class. After that, the instructor may ask students to name

specific parts of the fractions or specifically a related topic that they would like to learn more about. Giving students the opportunity to choose their own learning path not only improves their overall understanding of the material covered , but also sends a sense of the instructor's involvement with the students and trying to address their own interests.

- Having casual conversations with students on topics that interest them before, during and after class.

- Try to meet and talk to children outside of the school setting, such as extracurricular activities or the store.

Choose a small number of children from the group who eat in the cafeteria every day and chat with them.

- It is especially important to be aware of and pay attention to notable events in students' lives, such as taking part in sports, theater or other activities outside of the classroom.

- Students should be praised for their great achievements both inside and outside the classroom.

- Students should be greeted at the entrance when entering the classroom and each child should be greeted by name.

- You should make direct eye contact with each student. Teachers can keep eye contact while speaking if they scan the entire room and are allowed to move around in all areas of the room.

- During the lesson, make a concerted effort to approach and keep closeness to each student. It is essential that the seating arrangement eases smooth and unhindered movement throughout the space for both the instructor and the students.

Students who are hostile towards others often have poor anger management, a limited ability for empathy, and an inability to recognize the consequences of their behavior. Students who are considered dissenters may have less serious behavioral problems, but they persistently refuse to follow rules, argue with adults, use bad language, and tend to offend others. Students who fall into the hidden subcategory can sometimes be quite polite people; however, they are often in the area

where problems begin and never do exactly what authority figures want them to do. Providing quick incentives and results to aggressive learners and developing behavioral contracts with such learners are two other strategies that can help. To begin with, it is important for educators to keep in mind that there are still young people who experience a great deal of fear and suffering, even if they seem quite resistant to changing the behavior of aggressive children . This should always be kept in mind . Students who have difficulty concentrating can be divided into those who are hyperactive and those who are inattentive. These children may respond well when instructors make agreements with them to regulate behavior, teach them basic attention, study, and thinking skills, help them break down assignments into manageable chunks, praise their achievements, and appoint a peer tutor. Students who fall into the perfectionism category are pushed to excel at unattainable levels. They belittle themselves, suffer from poor self-esteem , and experience feelings of inferiority. Teachers are often able to help these students admit their mistakes, encourage them to set more realistic expectations for themselves, and give other students a chance to study. Students who struggle with their social skills have trouble making and keeping friendships. They may talk too much, stand too close to other people, and touch them disgustingly. They may also misunderstand statements made by others. These children can receive help from their teacher's guidance on proper behavior in social situations.

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